

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BEHAVIOR OF YOUNGER SCHOOL-AGE STUDENTS

Gabbarbergenova Jazira Damirovna

Karakalpak State University named after Berdaq.

L.Bektursinova

academic supervisor.

Associate Professor, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, PhD.

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Annotation. *This article analyzes changes in the behavior of school-age children from a psychological perspective. In today's society, the emotional state of children, social environment, technological factors and changes in the family climate affect their behavior on a scientific basis.*

Based on research, the causes of such states as aggressiveness, inattention, apathy or excessive activity in behavior are identified and effective psychological approaches to these states are recommended.

Keywords: *behavior, school age, social influence, family environment, technostress, child psychology.*

School age is an important stage in the socialization of a child, self-awareness and the formation of personal characteristics. In recent years, teachers, psychologists and parents have expressed concern about the significant changes in the behavior of school-age children. These changes include aggressiveness, social withdrawal, decreased attention, hyperactivity, and emotional instability.

Junior school age (approximately from 6-7 to 10-11 years old) is a turning point in a child's life. During this period, the play activity characteristic of kindergarten is replaced by systematic learning activity. The child not only acquires new knowledge, but also begins to understand his place in society. However, this transition period is not the same for all children.

Sharp psychological differences are noticeable in the behavior of students of junior school age.

Below we will analyze the main psychological differences in the behavior of children of this age, their causes and characteristics.

Differences in the behavior of a child are primarily associated with the type of his innate nervous system (temperament). Children who study in the same classroom under the same conditions react differently due to their temperament:

- Choleric and Sanguine children: They are active, quick to communicate. However, choleric students are often unstable, impatient and have difficulty sitting in one place for a long time in class. Impulsiveness (acting without thinking) dominates their behavior.

- Phlegmatic and Melancholic children: They are reserved, slow-moving and shy.

Melancholic children can quickly get worried and cry when the teacher gives a negative assessment or raises his voice, or become completely passive in class.

The Ecological Child Development Model (Bronfenbrenner, 2005) was also taken as a basis.

Socio-psychological factors: The instability of the family environment, the stress of parents, and the lack of attention to the child directly affect his emotional state. In today's modern society, the employment of parents, the increase in the number of divorces, and family conflicts lead to an increase in aggressiveness and depressive states in school-age children. 2. The impact of technological tools: Smartphones, computer games, and the endless flow of Internet content reduce children's attention span and distance them from real-life social interactions.

Such technological overload has a negative impact on the neuropsychic development of the child, especially between the ages of 6 and 12. This condition is called technostress and manifests itself in the form of excessive fatigue, aggression, or apathy in young children. School environment and the role of teachers: The teacher's approach to the child, whether he meets or ignores his emotional needs, has a great influence on how the child behaves. Fear of the teacher, lack of emotional closeness - can lead to passivity, rebellion or internal social isolation in the child's behavior.

Emotional intelligence and self-regulation: Insufficient development of the child's emotional sphere deprives him of the ability to correctly express his feelings. This leads to conflicts with other people.

The development of emotional intelligence is an important factor in psychological stability for school-age children. The above analysis shows that changes in children's behavior are a multifactorial, complex phenomenon that cannot be explained by only one reason. The main task of educators and psychologists today is to understand the child's internal state, establish emotional contact with him, identify the problems behind negative behavior, and formulate an individual approach. Ensuring psychological health in the family, strengthening psychological services in schools, and standardizing the use of technologies are among the main measures.

Changes in the behavior of school-age children are closely related to the rapidly developing psychological and social processes in modern society. Studies show that such conditions as aggression, apathy, attention deficit and emotional instability in children often arise as a result of the family environment, excessive dependence on technology, the psychological environment at school and pedagogical approaches. Early identification of such changes in behavior and taking appropriate psychological measures against them are crucial for the formation of a healthy child.

In such cases, family stability, the activity of the school psychological service, the emotional approach of the teacher and the development of the child's emotional intelligence are important factors. Negative behavioral changes can be prevented by supporting the child's personal development, creating a positive social environment and using technology wisely.

Therefore, it is necessary for the school and family to work together to pay attention to the mental health of children and lay the foundation for their socio-psychological development.

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